

THE EFFECTS OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON REFORM DEFORMATION AND TENSILE STRENGTH OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES IN SQUEEZE CASTING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Through a series of experiments with preforms that had randomly oriented fiber distribution, preform deformation and the tensile strength of metal matrix composites were investigated with variation of processing parameters. The scanning electron microscopy micrographs and optical micrographs are also presented for investigating the effects of processing parameters on the microstructures of metal matrix composites.

INTRODUCTION

The squeeze casting process is based on the injection of a fully liquid melt into the interstitial space within an assembly of ceramic fibers.^{[1]-[6]} For a practical use of squeeze casting processes, it is necessary to deal with the influence of the processing parameters on microstructure of metal matrix composites, then on the properties of composites. However, the preform deformation is inevitable to a certain extent in all infiltration processes except for casting aluminum alloy, and the optical micrographs of composites show that the no breakage of fiber was found for all applied pressure. Therefore, it is also necessary to investigate influence of processing parameters on preform deformation for wrought aluminum alloy. But it is a few research appears to have focused on preform deformation and the influence of processing parameters on microstructure in infiltration processing of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites. The focus of the present work is on infiltration processing of wrought aluminum alloy Al2024 matrix composites reinforced with Al₂O₃ discontinuous

short fibers to avoid preform deformation. The composites were synthesized for a range of processing parameters, and tensile strength and microstructures of the infiltrated samples were characterized as a function of processing parameters such as punch velocity, amounts of binder, preform temperature, fiber volume fraction and applied pressure. The squeeze cast experiments with preforms that had randomly oriented fiber distribution were also performed to examine the influence of processing parameters on the preform deformation.

Experimental Procedure

1. Fabrication of preforms

The short fibers used in this study were SAFFIL δ -alumina of 3 μm diameter. The preforms were prepared by pouring measured quantities of this slurry into a forming mold and subsequently using vacuum filtration and pressurizing process.^{[7]-[8]} The preforms with the fiber volume fraction of 10, 15, 20% were fabricated with the same volume by controlling of weight of binder, stirring time, vacuum pressure and volume of water. The preforms used in this study were 100mm in length by 24mm thickness and 24mm width.

2. Fabrication of Metal Matrix Composites

The matrix materials used in this study were wrought aluminum alloy of Al2024 for the poor fluidity compared to the casting aluminum alloy. The aluminum alloy was melted in a resistance furnace and maintained at preselected temperature of molten metal T_1 . A mold lubricant was sprayed to the inner surfaces of dies so that it would become easy to release metal matrix composites from the dies later. The schematic diagram of the apparatus used in squeeze casting processes for fabrication of MMCs are shown in Fig.1(a)-(d). The alumina preform was placed in the die cavity of Fig.1(a) and this assemble mold was heated in an electric furnace to $T_m=400$ °C. The measured quantity of molten alloy was poured into preheated die cavity of Fig.1(a)-(b). The ram attached to 500 kN hydraulic press was used to maintain the pressure during alloy infiltration into the preform, as shown in Fig.1(c). The ram speed, applied pressure, and holding time were controlled. Temperature of a punch and a die was measured by thermocouples inserted in the location of 1mm from the surfaces of the punch and the die, respectively. Specimens of unreinforced matrix alloy were also squeeze cast under identical conditions representing the fiber volume fraction $V_f=0\%$.

After retrieving the specimens from the die, as shown in Fig.1(d), the standard tensile specimens of 6mm diameter were prepared. After machining, both composite and matrix alloy were fused at 490°C for 1.5 hours, water-quenched and subsequently aged at 190°C for 12 hours. The tensile tests were conducted

on 100 kN hydraulic closed loop mechanical test system.

Fig.1 (a)-(d)Schematic illustration of squeeze casting process

Experimental Results and Discussion

An attempt was made to quantitatively measure the influence of various processing parameters on preform deformation and tensile strength achieved in aluminum alloy matrices. These parameter included weight of binder, preform temperature, fiber volume fraction, applied pressure, delay time and punch velocity. The infiltrated samples were sectioned longitudinally and the preform deformation was measured. Fig.2(a)-(b) shows typical appearance of an infiltrated preform and the definition of volume fraction after squeeze casting. The shape of the preform sectional area after infiltration is represented by A_{f2} . Though there is difference of thickness along the width of the preform, it is considered to be constant because the difference is very small compared to longitudinal direction. The volume fractions of deformed preform are defined as following.

$$V_{f2 \min} = H / (H - h_{\min}) \times V_f$$

$$V_{f2 \max} = H / (H - h_{\max}) \times V_f$$

$$V_{f2} = (A_{f1} / A_{f2}) \times V_f$$

Where H , h_{\min} and h_{\max} are initial preform thickness, minimum and maximum preform thickness after squeeze casting, respectively. A_{f1} and A_{f2} are cross sectional area of preform before and after infiltration, respectively.

And V_f is a fiber volume fraction before infiltration.

The punch velocity with time until punch surface contacts the molten metal is given in three ways V_1 , V_2 , and V_3 , as shown schematically in Fig. 3. Here, elapsed time until punch contacts the melts are named by delay time. In case of

Fig.2 (a)(b) Appearance of deformed preform and definition of volume fraction

$V_1=4-22.6$ mm/sec and $V_2=12$ mm/sec, delay time is same but initial pressurizing velocity is different. For the delay time $V_3=22.6$ mm/sec is short compared to $V_1=4-22.6$ mm/sec and $V_2=12$ mm/sec and initial pressurizing velocity is 22.6mm/sec. The results presented in Fig.4 shows variation of composites tensile strength for variation of punch velocity on conditions of the $T_p=800^\circ\text{C}$ and $W_b=20\%$. The maximum strength was obtained for composites fabricated for $V_3=22.6$ mm/sec. The strength of about 460 MPa has been observed. To find out cause of above results, microstructures were examined. The fiber distribution of fabricated composites with $V_1=4-22.6$ mm/sec was less uniform and more dense than that of composites fabricated in $V_3=22.6$ mm/sec, and fiber breakage is also investigated. This is assumed to be cause of tensile strength degradation in composites

Fig.3 Schematic diagram of punch velocity and delay time at the squeeze casting processes

Fig.4 Effects of the punch velocity condition on the ultimate strength of composites using Al2024 $W_b=20\%$ and $T_p=700^\circ\text{C}$

fabricated in $V_1=4-22.6$ mm/sec. Fig.5(a)-(b) show calculated volume fraction considering the preform deformation for three punch velocity conditions and an amount of binder percentage of preform weight $W_b=20\%$. Where T_m , T_p , and T_1 , represent the temperature of the mold, preform and molten melts, respectively, and P , L_f and V_f are applied pressure, fiber length and volume fraction,

respectively. Delay time affected preform deformation, namely the shorter delay time was, the smaller preform deformation was. It is assumed to be caused from the delay of solidification of melts. As can be seen from results of V_1 and V_2 , initial pressurizing velocity was not so important processing parameter as

Fig.5 (a)(b) Effects of the punch velocity condition on variation of the fiber volume fraction using Al2024 $W_b=20\%$ and $T_p=700^\circ\text{C}$

delay time to preform deformation. Fig.6(a)-(c) show the SEM fractographs for fracture surface of composites fabricated for variation of punch velocity. Fig.6(a)-(b) are not fully infiltration state between fibers and fibers. Namely, solidification is generated within the interstitial fibers before infiltration is

Fig.6 (a)-(c) SEM micrograph of composites fracture surface
 (a) $V_1=4-22.6 \text{ mm/sec}$
 (b) $V_2=12 \text{ mm/sec}$
 (c) $V_3=22.6 \text{ mm/sec}$

complete. The poor interface bonding between matrix and fiber is also investigated compared to fabricated composites with $V_3=22.6$ mm/sec, as shown in Fig.6(a)-(b). Therefore, fully infiltration states are essential for the improvement of mechanical properties in the fabrication process of metal matrix composites using wrought base aluminum alloy. The results presented in Fig.7 show the preform deformation with variation of the weight of binder under punch velocity $V_3=22.6$ mm/sec. Before experiment, preform deformation was expected to be decreased with the increase of binder, but there were no clear trends.

Fig.7 Effects of amounts of binder on the preform deformation of composites using Al2024

When the binder percentage of preform weight 10%, a binder was not also observed on the surfaces of fibers for 20%. But in the case of 30%, many lumps of binder were observed on the surface of fibers. Lumps of binder on the surface of fibers could be impurities in the interfaces between fibers and matrix materials and this is assumed to affect the strength degradation of composites. The effects of preheated preform temperature on preform deformation are shown in Fig.8. As preform temperature was higher, preform deformation was decreased. The decrease of heat loss from the melts due to high preform temperature resulted in the reduction of resistance for melts to flow into the interstitial space within an assembly of alumina fibers. With the increase of preform temperature, the tensile strength was decreased due to thermal deterioration of fibers. Some fiber breakage due to the excessive preform deformation is found in the fractured surfaces. Many fractures at the fiber surface are found in preform temperature of 700°C . It is assumed to reflect the thermal deterioration of fibers. So it is advised to maintain the preform temperature as low as possible within the range of good infiltration. With the increase of fiber volume fraction, as expected, preform deformation was decreased. It is thought to be resulted from the increase of preform stiffness.

Fig.8 Effects of the initial preform temperature on the variation of fiber volume fraction with Al2024 and punch velocity $V_3=22.5\text{mm/sec}$ correspond to the smallest preform deformation

Fig.9 shows the tensile strength of composites for variation of fiber volume fraction with punch velocity $V_3=22.6\text{ mm/sec}$. This represents remarkable improvement in composites strength compared to base aluminum alloy Al2024. For comparison, specimens of unreinforced matrix alloy were also cast under identical conditions. Irrespective of applied pressure, tensile strength is slightly increased with the increase of fiber volume fraction. Fig.10 shows the effects of applied pressure on the tensile strength of composites using matrix alloy of Al2024 for $V_f=15, 20\%$, $V_3=22.6\text{ mm/sec}$ and $W_b=20\%$. Though there is the slight decrease and the increase with pressure, as shown in the Fig.10, the difference is very small. Applied pressure does not seem to affect the tensile strength of composites remarkably.

Fig.9 Effects of initial fiber volume fraction on the ultimate strength of composites with Al2024

Fig.10 Effects of applied pressure on the ultimate strength for composites Al2024 for $V_f=15.20\%$, $W_b=20\%$ and $V_3=\text{mm/sec}$

CONCLUSIONS

1. Large preform deformation during infiltration can be the cause of lowering tensile strength due to breakage of fibers and poor filling of molten metal between fibers and fibers.
2. The tensile strength of composites is strongly dependent on fiber volume fraction and on the others of parameters more or less.
3. The excessive use of binder and high preform temperature reduce the tensile strength of composites.
4. The volume fraction variation remarkably depends on punch velocity than that of initial preform temperature, amount of binder and initial volume fraction.

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